

were followed. We recorded yield at 14% moisture level.

The regression of genotypes for average yield on the environmental index resulted in regression coefficients (b) ranging from -0.1677 to 2.0643 (see table). The coefficient of determination (r^2) ranged from 0.0224 to 0.9529. The deviation from regression mean squares

($S^2 d$), a true measure of genotypic stability, ranged from 0.0223 to 0.7997.

PK3717-9, PK3727-2, PK3717-12, PK3727-5, PK3849-18, and KS282 showed higher yields than the pooled means, but they had varied responses to environmental fluctuations. PK3727-2 and PK3727-5 were unstable for yield because of the significant values of b_i and $S^2 d$.

PK3717-9, PK3717-12, and PK3849-18 yielded higher than the pooled mean. These genotypes also showed non-significant values for b_i and $S^2 d$, indicating stable genotype interaction over three environments. They can be recommended for use in breeding programs aiming to develop cultivars with high yield potential and better adaptability. □

Genetic studies for allogamous traits in *oryza sativa* L.

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We studied the nature of the gene action of two traits—anther length and pollen grain size—in F_1 from a diallel cross involving the rice varieties and lines Basmati 370, Basmati 385, Basmati 198, and 4048.

We laid out the experiment during 1991 kharif in a randomized complete block design, with three replications, and a spacing of 30 cm between rows and plants. We measured anther length and pollen grain size using a binocular microscope and recorded 10 observations for both traits from each of the main panicles of 10 plants per replication for each genotype.

The components of variation (see table) revealed that additive component (D) exceeded the dominance components H_1 and H_2 for anther length, indicating additive type of gene action for increased anther length. The inverse, however, was true for pollen grain size. Recessive

Estimates of components of variation with their standard errors for anther length and pollen grain size in rice.

Anther length (mm)	Pollen grain size (μ)
$D \pm SE (D) = 0.0236 \pm 3.1623$	1.2795 ± 1.2669
$F \pm SE (F) = -0.0197 \pm 8.124$	1.3540 ± 3.2546
$H_1 \pm SE (H_1) = 0.0155 \pm 9.1924$	10.2192 ± 3.6826
$H_2 \pm SE (H_2) = 0.0090 \pm 8.4853$	8.0473 ± 3.3993
$h^2 \pm SE (h) = 4.0015 \pm 5.8310$	4.5319 ± 2.3305
$E \pm SE (E) = 0.002 \pm 0.4142$	0.727 ± 0.5666
Derived values	
$\sqrt{H_1/D}$	$= 0.8102 \quad 2.8261$
$H_2/4H_1$	$= 0.1457 \quad 0.1969$
$[\{4DH\}^{1/2} + F]/[\{4DH\}^{1/2} - F]$	$= 0.32 \quad 1.512$
h^2/H	$= -0.163 \quad 0.563$

alleles were important for anther length whereas more dominant alleles were observed for pollen grain size in parent varieties. H_1 and H_2 were not similar in both traits, showing that positive and negative allele frequencies were unequal.

The mean degree of dominance, 0.81 and 2.83, indicated partial dominance for anther length and overdominance for pollen grain size. The ratio of H_2 to $4H_1$

(0.14, 0.20) showed unequal positive and negative allele frequencies for both traits. The ratio h^2 to H_2 indicated that no dominant gene was controlling anther length whereas at least one gene controlling pollen grain size exhibited some dominance. This information will be useful in designing future hybrid rice breeding programs. □

Inheritance of aroma in two aromatic rice varieties

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Jin-Long Dao and 80-66 are two later maturing aromatic rice varieties developed by HRRRI. We made reciprocal

crosses between these scented varieties and nonscented rice varieties HA8857 and Xiang Zao Xian no. 1 and 3 in 1989 to study aroma inheritance.

We sowed the F_1 and F_2 progeny and the parents from these crosses in Apr 1990 and transplanted them in May 1990. Thirty plants of each parent, 30 F_1 plants from each reciprocal cross, and about 200 F_2 plants of each cross from the four

Scent ratings of F_1 , F_2 , and parents, HRRRI, Changsha, China, 1990.

Entry	Plants (no.)			χ^2 (3:1)	P
	Total	Nonscented	Scented		
Parent					
Jin-Long Dao	30	0	30		
80-66	30	0	30		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
HA8557	30	30	0		
F_1					
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
Jin-Long Dao/HA8557	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
HA8557/Jin-Long Dao	30	30	0		
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	30	30	0		
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	30	30	0		
80-66/HA8557	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 1/80-66	30	30	0		
Xiang zao Xian no. 3/80-66	30	30	0		
HA8557/80-66	30	30	0		
F_2					
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	186	143	43	0.2580	0.50-0.75
Jin-Long Dao/Xiang zao Xian no. 3	160	124	36	0.4083	0.50-0.75
80-66/Xiang zao Xian no. 1	142	105	37	0.0375	>0.90
80-66/HA8557	161	124	37	0.4083	0.50-0.75